

DISTANCE FORMS OF EDUCATION IN TEACHING SPECIAL SUBJECTS.

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Abstract: The experience of creating a distance education system shows that education through a computer network is a developing system based on its basis. In recent years, computer telecommunication networks are developing rapidly. For their effective use, it is necessary to further improve methodological support.

Key words: Moderator, Tutor, Adviser, Facilitator, Invigilator, "University of the Future" CityU MOOK, UdacityX, Open Polytechnics, MOOC Iversity, Informatization of the educational process, Development of intellectual and creative abilities of the individual, Education of every member of society ability to improve one's skills and change the field of activity.

Today's information and telecommunication tools allow students to choose each subject according to the level of difficulty, as well as study them according to their interests and career plans. This situation will change the old views in education that have been preserved from the past. The method of distance education passes the borders of our Republic, communicates with the Commonwealth of Independent States and major educational centers of the world level, and serves to create a new modern integrated educational opportunity for education. In this regard, significant work is being done in the educational institutions of our country. In particular, in all the prestigious universities located in our capital, our students had the opportunity to learn from the leading professors, teachers and experts working in other countries of the world. In addition, the current system has the ability to quickly deliver new knowledge and experiences, increase the economic efficiency of education, and wide use of audio-video, animation, and graphics in the educational process. It is also planned to open a distance learning higher education institution in Uzbekistan - "Kelajak University" with the participation of foreign investors such as CityU MOOC (Hong Kong), UdacityX (USA), Open Polytechnics (New Zealand) and MOOC Iversity (Netherlands). is being held. The project envisages the introduction of advanced pedagogical and information technologies, the latest achievements of science and techniques into the higher education process. Of course, this includes electronic information and educational resources (translated into Uzbek and Russian) and educational programs by students (around 50,000 per year), regardless of where they are. , it is necessary to create conditions for the operation of the electronic information-educational environment that ensures their mastery. The term "distance education" could not find a stable place in the sources created in Russian and English languages. This concept is also used in options such as "distance education", "distance learning".

Distance education - educational services provided remotely to a wide range of the country's population and foreign countries using a specialized information environment based on means of educational information exchange (satellite satellite, television, radio,

computer communication, etc.) is a set. The information-educational environment of distance learning consists of information, information resources, communication statements, software documents aimed at meeting the needs of users for education, and a set of organizational and methodological support.

Distance education is one of the forms of continuous education, focused on ensuring the right of a person to receive education and information.

Distance education is a new structure of the educational process based on the principle of independent learning of the student. A learning environment is characterized by the fact that learners are often or always distant in space (or time) from the teacher. At the same time, they will have the opportunity to communicate using telecommunication tools at any time.

It is considered that the technology of distance education was formed for the first time in 1969 at the initiative of the Prime Minister of Great Britain G. Wilson. In more than 75% of higher education institutions in the USA, a similar teaching system was used in the mid-60s of the last century.

In Europe, distance education began to develop rapidly in the early 70s in the USA, Great Britain, Germany, France, Australia and many other countries. Currently, the number of educational institutions that have introduced distance learning in European countries has increased significantly.

In particular, NTV National University of Technology of the USA, OU - Open and Surrey Universities of Great Britain, SNED - National Distance Education Center of France, International Association of Euro-Asia Distance Education, Russian Institute of Information, Russian Institute of System Integration, Institute of Educational Information, the laboratory and institute of the Russian Academy of Education, the Federal Center for Distance Education, the Center for Information and Analytical Support of Distance Education, etc.

The leading higher education institutions of countries such as USA, Canada, Great Britain, Germany and France have their own telecomputer system. New information technologies are used more in regional associations. One of the contradictions of the modern system is the rapid increase in knowledge and the limited ability of an individual to master it. This conflict requires abandoning the absolute ideal of "comprehensive development of a person" in the pedagogical theory and accepting a new ideal - the ideal of maximum manifestation of a person's identity or "independent education and maturity". If the educational technologies are not changed, then it is possible to imagine what kind of knowledge and what skills the experts will have. Students acquire knowledge 40-60% faster and in a shorter period of time with the help of information and communication technologies than with conventional technologies. That's why distance education is developing very fast all over the world.

The global trend of transitioning to distance education is taking place with the increase in the number of educational institutions that train personnel on this technology.

The experience of creating a distance education system shows that education through a computer network is a developing system based on its basis. In recent years, computer telecommunication networks are developing rapidly. For their effective use, it is necessary to further improve methodological support.

Currently, computer technologies become an integral part of the educational process, and the issue of creating an information-educational system is being raised in every

educational institution. This system plays the role of both a teacher and an educator and becomes a quick source of information for educational and practical purposes. Its task is to technically manage the educational process, to analyze and determine the quality and quantity indicators of education, to ensure the effectiveness of education (Fig. 1).

Informatization of the educational process

Currently, educational and methodological support in the form of case technology has been developed for the independent study of the presented material. It includes textbooks, recommendations for their use, and various demonstration manuals.

Distance education is a process connecting a teacher and a student located in different geographical regions, and communication is carried out using special technologies. Various methods are used for communication: exchange of typographic printed materials by mail and fax, audio conference, video conference, virtual conference by computer. Distance education among those who live far from the educational institution, those who do not have the conditions to attend school, those who want to improve their qualifications, the disabled and those who for various other reasons do not have the opportunity to receive education directly in higher educational institutions and it is natural that the demand for education will increase. Distance education is a very convenient tool, especially for working adults and those who want to learn a second specialty.

The following trends are also important in the development of distance education:

1. An increase in the number of educational institutions that provide professional training information using new information technologies;
2. Mutual coordination of organizational systems of educational institutions.

Analyzing the basis of distance education, it is possible to come to the following conclusions noted in Figure 2

Figure 2.**Analysis of the basics of distance education**

The quality of education, which characterizes distance education with five main conditions:

- interaction between teacher and student;
- that the teacher and students are at a certain distance from each other;
- two-way communication between teachers and students;
- availability of special materials for distance learning;
- that both sides are provided with computers and other equipment and communications

The activities of teachers in the organization of distance education are not limited only to the transmission of educational information. For this reason, several specialists are involved in the organization of this type of education. They are named differently according to their functions. In particular:

1. The teacher is the author of the educational and methodological manuals used in the organization of distance education.
2. Moderator - independent thinking and work of distance learners develops abilities, activates cognitive activities.
3. Tutor (lat. "tutorem") - teacher, trainer who chooses interactive methods for training courses, establishes an educational relationship between the lecturer and the student.
4. Adviser (fr. "avisen" - "to think", "advisor" - "thinker") is a consultant who provides methodical assistance to students during their individual, independent performance.
5. Facilitator (lat. "facilis", visual. "facilitator" - easy, convenient) - a pedagogue who develops the communication of distance learners, as well as objectively and effectively evaluates the activities of groups.
6. Invigilator - specialist-pedagogue who monitors the results of training organized on the basis of distance education.

It is known that, according to the principle of orientation of education to educational and developmental tasks, the teacher develops the educational and developmental potential of the lesson on a specific topic while forming certain knowledge, skills and competencies in students. it is meant not to forget.

Distance education in its development stage has shown itself to be one of the factors causing serious changes in higher education in the future. At this point, it is one of the

important issues to study the relative advantages and convenience of other forms of distance education, including its positive impact on increasing the quality and effectiveness of education.

Distance education is currently entering a new stage of development on a global scale. This is mainly due to the fact that while the basic technology and methods of teaching remain unchanged, new technical tools are developing and becoming available to the masses.

Figure 3.

Development strategies of distance education

New information technologies make serious demands on the quality and level of the educational process. The educational process is significantly optimized through the use of information technologies. They also ensure the implementation of two main principles, i.e. integration and technology.

The use of information technologies and telecommunication tools in the field of distance education can be maximally effective only when technical, technological, informational, normative, organizational and other elements of the distance education process are mutually developed.

In conclusion, it should be said that distance education did not happen all at once. The development process took place slowly. With the emergence of new technologies of imparting knowledge, it has been used in the distance education system, and its various forms have been developing. By now, it has taken the form of a model based on completely multimedia materials, including various generations of distance learning technologies and multimedia. All this is the result of technologies not replacing each other, but complementing each other.

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